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HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF DEVELOPMENT AND DYNAMICS OF ATTITUDES TOWARDS WIND ENERGY

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Abstract

The article considers the problem of increasing the energy efficiency of power plants using renewable energy sources, which remains one of the priority tasks to be solved in the energy sector. The development of the main directions for improving the energy efficiency of generating systems and power supply systems is associated with determining the causes of the irrational use of energy resources. In recent years, due to the increase in the consumption of electrical energy in industry and agriculture, there has been a shortage of produced electrical energy. Increasing the volume of electricity production by traditional methods leads to a deterioration in the environmental situation (increase in carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere, depletion of hydrocarbon reserves).

Keywords: energy, agriculture, land, thermal installations, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the mid-1980s, the USSR adopted the "Energy Program of the USSR", which noted that the country was beginning to run out of recoverable and convenient oil reserves. Further growth in energy production in the next 20-30 years should be provided mainly at the expense of coal, including low-grade coal, and more and more - nuclear fuel. Further, one can presumably hope for a technological breakthrough in the field of the development of thermonuclear fusion energy and the development of renewable energy sources. The need to change the orientation in the structure of the country's energy balance is recognized by many specialists and experts, however, practical implementation is postponed until better times.

In May 1995, the Decree "On the main directions of energy policy and restructuring of the fuel industry of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2015" was signed. This Decree approved the program "Energy Strategy of Russia" developed under the leadership of the Ministry of Fuel and Energy - the successor to the Energy Program of the USSR. In the new program, the energy industry is mainly focused on the use of gas, due to the forced production of which it is planned to restructure the rest of the fuel industry.

II. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

As a methodological basis, a system analysis was used, which makes it possible to identify direct and feedback links of the object under study with interacting factors with a non-rectilinear dependence that have a significant impact on the energy parameters of the object being developed. In the article, based on the formulation of the tasks to be solved and taking into account the characteristics of the object under study, both theoretical and experimental research methods were used in obtaining the main results.

In Russia, wind energy began to develop more than a century ago. It all started with the study of vortices, lift and wings. The Russian mathematician Nikolai Yegorovich Zhukovsky played a decisive role in these studies. Of course, the achievements were primarily used in aviation, which is why Zhukovsky is still called the father of Russian aviation to this day. But in parallel, he and his students worked on the theory of wind turbines.

By the 1930s, a wind energy research center had appeared in the country. In 1931 - the first experimental wind turbine with a wind wheel with a diameter of 30 m and a generator with a capacity of 400 kW. By the middle of the century, more than 40 thousand wind turbines were produced, which were used on collective farms and state farms.

Until the end of the 1980s, wind energy in Russia was actively developing. And today it is experiencing its renaissance.

Thanks to the vast expanses of the country, Russia has the world's largest technical, electrical and wind energy potential. According to experts, it is about 17100 MW/h per year, for Germany, for example, this figure is approximately equal to 2800.

Various regions and regions of Russia in almost all federal districts are considered promising regions for the development of wind energy. Kalmykia, Krasnodar and Stavropol Territories, Rostov, Volgograd, Astrakhan and Leningrad regions deserve special attention, although other regions should not be discounted, up to the Far Eastern Federal District, including Kamchatka and Sakhalin.

Considering the wind energy in Russia as an alternative to traditional energy, it should not be perceived as a replacement, but only as an addition. The main reasons for the increased interest in it can be considered:

the transition of world countries to the so-called hydrogen economy - RES can be easily considered as its component;

the huge energy potential of the country's wind energy industry, which makes it possible to include this area of WNA in the country's strategic energy plans;

quick payback of domestic wind farms - estimated figures usually do not exceed 10 years;

relative simplicity and high speed of construction of wind farms;

expanding the capabilities of the Rosatom corporation, which has various solutions in its arsenal, ranging from nuclear energy to renewable energy.

It is no coincidence that wind energy is becoming part of the energy strategy of the Russian Federation.

Energy wind zones in Russia are located mainly on the coast and islands of the Arctic Ocean from the Kola Peninsula to Kamchatka, in the regions of the Lower and Middle Volga and Don, the coast of the Caspian, Okhotsk, Barents, Baltic, Black and Azov seas. Separate wind zones are located in Karelia, Altai, Tuva, Baikal. The maximum average wind speed in these areas occurs in the autumn-winter period, the period of greatest demand for electricity and heat. About 30% of the economic potential of wind energy is concentrated in the Far East, 14% - in the Northern economic region, about 16% - in Western and Eastern Siberia. The total installed capacity of wind power plants in the country in 2009 was 17-18 MW.

In the 1890s, the Danish scientist Poul la Cour designed wind turbines to generate electricity, which what then used to produce hydrogen.

The largest wind power plant in Russia (5.1 MW) is located near the village of Kulikovo, Zelenogradsky district, Kaliningrad region. Zelenograd wind turbine consists of 21 installations of the Danish company SEAS Energi Service A.S.

In Chukotka, there is the Anadyr wind farm with a capacity of 2.5 MW (10 wind turbines of 250 kW each). Annual output in 2015 did not exceed 0.2 million kWh.

In the Republic of Bashkortostan, Tyupkildy wind farm with a capacity of 2.2 MW operates, located near the village of the same name in the Tuymazinsky district. The wind farm consists of four wind turbines of the German company Hanseatische AG type ET 550/41 with a capacity of 550 kW each. Annual electricity generation in 2008-2010 did not exceed 0.4 million kWh. In Kalmykia, 20 km from Elista, the site of the Kalmyk wind farm was located with a planned capacity of 22 MW and an annual output of 53 million kWh; in 2006, one Raduga unit with a capacity of 1 MW and an output of 3 to 5 million kWh was installed on the site. In the Republic of Komi, near Vorkuta, the Zapolyarnaya VDES with a capacity of 3 MW has not been completed. In 2006, there are 6 units of 250 kW with a total capacity of 1.5 MW.

On the Bering Island of the Commander Islands, there is a wind farm with a capacity of 1.2 MW. A successful example of the implementation of the capabilities of wind turbines in difficult climatic conditions is a wind-diesel power plant at Cape Set-Navolok of the Kola Peninsula with a capacity of up to 0.1 MW. In 2009, 17 kilometers from it, a survey of the parameters of the future wind farm operating in conjunction with the Kislogubskaya TPP was started. There are projects at different stages of development of the Leningrad WPP 75 MW Leningrad Region, Yeysk WPP 72 MW Krasnodar Territory, Kaliningrad Marine WPP 50 MW, Morskoy WPP 30 MW Karelia, Primorskoy WPP 30 MW Primorsky Territory, Magadan WPP 30 MW Magadan Region, Chui WPP 24 MW Republic of Altai, Ust-Kamchatskoy VPS 16 MW Kamchatka Oblast, Novikovskoy VPS 10 MW Republic of Komi, Dagestanskoy WPP 6 MW Dagestan, Anapskoy WPP 5 MW Krasnodar Territory, Novorossiysk WPP 5 MW Krasnodar Territory and Valaamskoy WPP 4 MW Karelia.

As an example of realizing the potential of the territories of the Sea of Azov, one can point to the Novoazovskaya wind farm, operating in 2010 with a capacity of 21.8 MW.

In 2003-2020, within the framework of RAO UES, experiments were carried out to create complexes based on wind turbines and internal combustion engines; under the program, one unit was installed in the village of Tiksi. All projects started in RAO related to wind energy were transferred to RusHydro. At the end of 2018, RusHydro began searching for promising sites for the construction of wind farms.

Attempts were made to mass-produce wind turbines for individual consumers, for example, the Romashka water-lifting unit.

In recent years, the increase in capacity has been mainly due to low-power individual power systems, the sales volume of which is 250 wind turbines (with a capacity of 1 kW to 5 kW).

Wind power is an unregulated source of energy. The output of a wind farm depends on the strength of the wind, a factor that is highly variable. Accordingly, the output of electricity from the wind turbine to the power system is highly uneven both in daily and weekly, monthly, annual and long-term sections. Considering that the energy system itself has load inhomogeneities (peaks and dips in energy consumption), which, of course, cannot be regulated by wind energy, the introduction of a significant share of wind energy into the energy system contributes to its destabilization. It is clear that wind energy requires a reserve of power in the energy system (for example, in the form of gas turbine power plants), as well as mechanisms for smoothing the heterogeneity of their generation (in the form of hydroelectric power plants or pumped storage power plants). This feature of wind energy significantly increases the cost of electricity received from them. Grids are reluctant to connect wind turbines to the grid, which has led to legislation requiring them to do so.

Problems in the networks and dispatching of power systems due to the instability of the operation of wind turbines begin after they reach a share of 20-25% of the total installed capacity of the system. For Russia, this will be an indicator close to 50 thousand - 55 thousand MW.

According to the Spanish companies Gamesa Eolica and WinWind, the accuracy of forecasts for the generation of energy from wind farms during hourly planning in the day-ahead market or spot mode exceeds 95%.

Small stand-alone wind turbines may have problems with the network infrastructure, since the cost of the transmission line and switchgear to connect to the power grid may be too high. The problem is partially solved if the wind turbine is connected to a local network where there are energy consumers. In this case, the existing power and distribution equipment is used, and the WPP creates some power boost, reducing the power consumed by the local network from the outside. The transformer substation and the external transmission line are less loaded, although the total power consumption may be higher.

Large wind turbines experience significant repair problems, since replacing a large part (blade, rotor, etc.) at a height of more than 100 meters is a complex and expensive undertaking.

Currently, despite the increase in energy prices, the cost of electricity does not amount to any significant amount for the bulk of production compared to other costs; reliability and stability of power supply remain key for the consumer.

The main factors leading to an increase in the cost of energy received from wind turbines are:

The need to obtain industrial-quality electricity ~ 220V 50 Hz (requires the use of an inverter)

The need for autonomous operation for some time (requires the use of batteries)

The need for long-term uninterrupted operation of consumers (requires the use of a diesel generator)

Currently, it is most economically feasible to obtain with the help of wind turbines not industrial-quality electrical energy, but direct or alternating current (variable frequency), followed by its conversion with the help of heating elements into heat, for heating housing and obtaining hot water.

The scale of today's changes in the energy sector is well demonstrated by another comparison: the global wind power capacity built in 2015 alone exceeds the total installed capacity of Russian hydroelectric power plants and is twice as large as all operating nuclear power plants in the Russian Federation. These figures prove that wind power has become an important way of generating electricity not only in industrialized countries, but also in developing countries. The history of the development of modern wind power is the history of the growth of the size and power of wind turbines.

The growth in the size of wind turbines since 1980.

The development of science and technology, the improvement of technologies for planning the placement of wind power plants have led to the fact that in the "unstable" wind power industry, a sufficiently high coefficient of installed capacity utilization (CIUM) is provided today. Taking into account the growing economic attractiveness of wind energy, combined with the virtually unlimited wind energy resources of the planet, it is theoretically possible to supply the whole of mankind with electricity, almost entirely produced only on the basis of wind. A study from Harvard University, based on very conservative assumptions, shows that the potential for wind power is about 40 times greater than global electricity consumption.

Installed capacity of wind power plants in the world, GW.

The average annual growth rate of global wind power capacity since 2014 is 21.4% per year, and over the past decade, its installed capacity has grown eight times. At the end of 2015, it amounted to 370 GW, and, presumably, by 2024 it will reach 1500 GW.

III. CONCLUSION

Almost all experts recognize the economic feasibility of introducing new wind power plants in Russia. At the same time, today there are a number of barriers to the development, implementation and large-scale use of wind energy. These are insufficient state support, the lack of a wind energy development program and incentives to invest in the industry, underdeveloped infrastructure and a lack of qualified personnel.

Wind energy has immense economic and social prospects. It ensures the promotion of business and civilization in areas with low population density, opens up new opportunities for their development, does not require water consumption and is a significant contribution to the energy security of the state.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ПРЕДПОСЫЛКИ РАЗВИТИЯ И ДИНАМИКА ОТНОШЕНИЯ К ВЕТРОЭНЕРГЕТИКЕ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается проблема повышения энергоэффективности электростанций, использующих возобновляемые источники энергии, которая остается одной из приоритетных задач, требующих решения в энергетическом секторе. Разработка основных направлений повышения энергоэффективности генерирующих систем и систем электроснабжения связана с определением причин нерационального использования энергоресурсов. В последние годы, в связи с увеличением потребления электрической энергии в промышленности и сельском хозяйстве, наблюдается дефицит производимой электрической энергии. Увеличение объемов производства электроэнергии традиционными методами приводит к ухудшению экологической обстановки (увеличению выбросов углекислого газа в атмосферу, истощению запасов углеводородов).

Ключевые слова: энергетика, сельское хозяйство, земля, тепловые установки, общество.

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